

Microscopic Calcification of Placenta in Pregnancy Induced HypertensionAnup Shyamal¹, Sanket Dadarao Hiware², Arnab Bhattacharya³, Anubhab Shyamal⁴, Pradeep Bokariya⁵, Sanjib Kumar Patra⁶¹Associate Professor, Anatomy MJN Medical College, Cooch Behar, West Bengal.²Assistant Professor, Anatomy, Graphic Era Institute of Medical Sciences, Dehradun, India.³Assistant Professor Department of Anatomy I.P.G.M.E. & R. and S.S.K.M. Hospital.⁴MBBS - Student, IQ City Medical College, Durgapur, West Bengal.⁵Associate Professor Department of Anatomy Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences Sevagram, Maharashtra.⁶Head of Department, Interventional Cardiology, Desun Heart Institute Kolkata.

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Abstract:

Introduction: Rise of blood pressure during pregnancy (gestational hypertension or pregnancy induced hypertension- 'PIH') is one of the most common causes of altered physiological process in pregnancy. There are very few scientific works in support of such hypotheses. Since placenta acts as a mirror to the disease process in mother and fetus or both we decided to study gross and microscopic placental structure in PIH.

Aim: The principal aim of the present study was to perform a case-control study on comparison of morphological and histological examination of placentae obtained by delivery of pregnant mothers who suffered from pregnancy induced hypertension (as 'PIH' cases) with that of placentae obtained from delivery of pregnant mothers who had an uneventful ante-natal period (as 'normal' controls). To record and compare relevant histomorphometric details of two groups of placentae and to evaluate the data for statistical significance in order to reach at a conclusion.

Materials and Methods: The present study entitled "Morphological & histological study of placenta in pregnancy with hypertension" was undertaken at department of Anatomy with co-operation of department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology of our Institution. The chief study material was placenta. Forty (40) placentae were collected from Institutional labour room immediately after term delivery of mothers having uneventful antenatal period (as control 'C'). Another forty (40) placentae were collected after term delivery of pregnant mothers who had clinically proven hypertension (pregnancy induced hypertension- PIH) during antenatal period [as cases or Experimental 'E']. Serial numbers were given to all the placentae of each group and all the entries were made with reference to same number throughout.

Method of Histo-Morphometry: To quantify certain parameters we did morphometric study in histological sections. We used square and linear graticules (Haugh 1955) to be fitted in microscope ocular and stage micrometer to calibrate the linear graticule.

Results: Volume Proportion of Calcification: The control placentae were showing the mean volume proportion of calcification 0.645 and the figure in PIH placenta was 4.954. The increased calcification in PIH cases was statistically significant.

Conclusion: There was significantly increased of volume proportion of calcified areas was significantly increased in experimental group of placentae.

Keywords: Pregnancy Hypertension Placenta Microcalcification.

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Introduction

Placenta is the organ belonging to the developing mammalian conceptus which is never incorporated in the body of foetus but it is vital to the well-being of the baby in the womb and it offers protective, nutritional, respiratory, synthetic and excretory functions as well. Thus it exists as a vital link between mother and developing fetus. Placenta is basically chorionic tissue and trophoblasts are the representative cells belong to. [1,2] The placental

trophoblasts subserve to provide all essential requirements of a successful pregnancy such as implantation, hormone synthesis, supply of nutrition and exchange of gas and metabolite between mother and fetus, immunological protection to fetus, maternal vascular blood flow increment into the placenta and initiation and promotion of parturition. Hence trophoblasts are responsible for a successful outcome of pregnancy-

a healthy baby and healthy mother, at the completion of intra-uterine life. [3,4]

Rise of blood pressure during pregnancy (gestational hypertension or pregnancy induced hypertension- 'PIH') is one of the most common causes of altered physiological process in pregnancy. [5]

The diagnosis of gestational hypertension is made in women whose blood pressure reaches 140/90 mm Hg or greater for the first time during pregnancy. In mild PIH the lady remains symptom free. When PIH presents with associated features like edema, proteinuria, headache, upper abdominal pain, easy fatigability, blurred vision, insomnia, blood dyscrasia etc it is termed pre-eclamptic toxemia (PET) and when convulsion occur it is the most severe form of PIH designated as Eclampsia of pregnancy which has grave prognosis. [6,7] Gestational hypertension is called transient hypertension if preeclampsia does not develop and the blood pressure returns to normal by 12 weeks postpartum. Rise of blood pressure during the later half of pregnancy is dangerous especially to the fetus. [8-12]

A number of hypotheses have been proposed to explain the aetiology of PIH. According to Sibai (2003) it is-

1. Abnormal trophoblastic invasion of uterine vessels.
2. Immunological intolerance between maternal and foeto-placental tissues.
3. Maternal mal-adaptation to cardiovascular or inflammatory changes of normal pregnancy.
4. Dietary deficiencies.
5. Genetic influences.

There are very few scientific works in support of such hypotheses. Since placenta acts as a mirror to the disease process in mother and fetus or both we decided to study microscopic placental structure in PIH.

Aim and Objectives

The principal aim of the present study was to perform a case-control study on comparison of histological examination of placentae obtained by delivery of pregnant mothers who suffered from pregnancy induced hypertension (as 'PIH' cases) with that of placentae obtained from delivery of pregnant mothers who had an uneventful ante-natal period (as 'normal' controls).

The objectives of the study were as under:

- To study and compare histological features of two groups of placentae after staining with Haematoxylin and Eosin (H and E), Masson's

Trichrome and Periodic acid and Schiff's method (PAS) by light microscopy and microphotography.

- To record and compare relevant histomorphometric details of two groups of placentae and to evaluate the data for statistical significance in order to reach at a conclusion.

Material and Methods

The present study entitled "Morphological & histological study of placenta in pregnancy with hypertension" was undertaken at department of Anatomy with co-operation of department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology of our Institution.

Prior approval of 'Institutional Human Ethics Committee' was duly obtained before starting the work.

The chief study material was placenta. Forty (40) placentae were collected from Institutional labour room immediately after term delivery of mothers having uneventful antenatal period (as control 'C'). Another forty (40) placentae were collected after term delivery of pregnant mothers who had clinically proven hypertension (pregnancy induced hypertension- PIH) during antenatal period [as cases or Experimental 'E']. Serial numbers were given to all the placentae of each group and all the entries were made with reference to same number throughout.

Inclusion criteria for all subjects:

- Age of mother between 20 to 38 years
- Subject must be registered in Institutional Hospital

Specific inclusion criterion for subjects enrolled as cases (experimental):

- Clinically proven hypertension in antenatal (beyond 20 weeks of gestation) or in intranatal period.

Inclusion criteria for Subjects enrolled as controls (normal pregnancy)

- Subjects free from any pre-existing clinical disorder.
- Uneventful antenatal period

Exclusion criteria for Subjects enrolled as experiment:

- Hypertension with other gestational disorders, pre-existing hypertension, subjects having still birth, gross congenital anomalies in baby, complicated vaginal delivery, emergency lower segment caesarean section, invasive procedure during gestation

Materials Required for Present Study:

Measuring tape, electronic weighing machine, measuring cylinder, long pithing needle, dissecting table, transparent polythene sheet, scalpel with blade, forceps, hard glass surface, tissue capsules, formal saline solution, graded alcohol, chloroform, soft and hard paraffin, wax bath, 'L' moulds, spirit lamp, glycerin, with rotary microtome (Cambridge type), knife handle, water bath, egg albumin, forceps, spatula, glass slides, slide slanting rack, slide warmer, diamond pencil, staining rack with all reagents recently prepared in glass bottle for routine and special stains, stop watch, cover slip, xylene, spatula, gauze piece and DPX, binocular microscope with arrangement of camera for microphotography.

Methods of tissue processing & section cutting

Collection of placenta: Each placenta was collected soon after delivery from the labour room or from the operation theatre. Placenta as a whole was kept in normal saline in a large container with snugly fitting lid. Then specimen was transported to research laboratory of Anatomy department.

Preparation for examination of placentae:

- Whole of the specimen of placenta was taken out from the large container and kept on a clean flat surface on the dissection table wrapped with a sheet of polythene.
- The specimen was washed well with normal saline and the membrane was trimmed off with a pair of sharp scissors near the margin.
- The specimen was soaked with blotting paper and excess blood clot was removed from the surface.
- The umbilical cord was cut at a distance of 2 cm from its attachment with placenta (Aherne and Dunhill, 1966).

The intact sample of placenta was kept for one week in 10% formal saline for fixation and hardening so as to make it suitable for cutting into 2-3 cm pieces for further routine histological processing followed by section cutting, staining, microscopy and microphotography.

All quantitative tabulated data was subjected to statistical analysis by student 't' test.

Section cutting and staining: From each block 100 serial sections of 5-6 micron thickness were cut in a ribbon by rotary microtome. The sections were floated in water bath (55°C); four to five consecutive sections were taken on one glass slide to which egg albumin was previously applied; slides were dried by keeping it on a slant and scored with a code number by diamond pencil. At a time only one block was processed to minimize the error of mixing of tissues.

The paraffin sections were placed over slide warmer immediately before staining for fixations of tissue with glass slides.

One set of slides was stained with haematoxylin and eosin and the other set by Masson's Trichrome and PAS.

Method of Light Microscopy

(Based on Hamilton and Boyd, 1970)

The stained slides of placentae of two groups were examined under binocular light microscope under different magnifications. The following parameters were studied and recorded from both group of samples & compared

1. Basal plate
2. Chorionic plate
3. The intermediate area represented by Chorionic villi and Intervillous space

Light microscopy is performed under different magnifications (X 100 with low power; X 400 in high power and X 1000 with oil immersion) under self-illuminated binocular microscope. Hematoxylin and Eosin (H/E) staining is performed routinely while Masson's trichrome; PAS or any other staining is done incidentally. In each slide all the serial sections are observed under microscope. H/E stained sections are used for screening of the slide and any special feature of interest by resolved under special stain (Masson's trichrome and PAS). Slide is screened in 'Z' manner so as to represent the whole cut section. Special attention is paid to the cells, stroma and blood vessels in the chorionic plate, basal plate and terminal villi. As the orientation of the sections is such that the basal plates and chorionic plates are always at the two extremes of the sections (except when sections are taken from margin of placenta) the intervening area contains sections of chorionic villi and the intervillous space.

- **Calcification (microscopic):** Amorphous discrete basophilic matter present in villi of term placenta signifies calcification (Microphotograph No.11 and 14).

Method of Histo-Morphometry: To quantify certain parameters we did morphometric study in histological sections. We used square and linear graticules (Haugh 1955) to be fitted in microscope ocular and stage micrometer to calibrate the linear graticule. (Figure no 6,7 and 8)

Calibration of Linear graticule: The length of each division of linear graticule was standardized with coinciding it with the stage micrometer under each objective lens of the same microscope. The dimension of one small division of stage micrometer was 10 micron. 6 divisions of stage

micrometer coincided with 16 divisions of ocular micrometer under 40X (high power) objective; therefore 1 division of ocular micrometer measured 6/16 micron (equals 0.0375 microns).

Haugh's graticule: The graticule contains 22 lines (11 horizontal and 11 vertical) intersecting to form a big square with 100 small squares and 100 intersecting points between them (including the points on upper and left arms of big square and excluding the points on right and lower arm of big square). Then the detailed morphometry was performed taking in to account the point of interest (whose morphometry is being done) coinciding with the intersecting points of the grid (Culling, 1968) while the rest falling outside the intersecting points though within the square, were excluded (Figure 6).

Five fields of ten sections of each placenta were examined (50 fields of each placenta) for histomorphometry of all the parameters.

Methods of Histomorphometry were applied for:

1. Calculation of Volume proportion of a given parameter.
2. Counting Number of a given parameter in a unit area of placenta

1. Method of Calculation of volume proportion:

(Based on Delesse principle, 1848)

This method was applicable for calculation of the parameters like VP of terminal villi, VP of fibrinoid degeneration and VP of Calcification. This figure gives the proportion of the placental area occupied by a particular parameter. This is expressed in percent.

Following formula was used for determination of volume proportion

$$V_p = \frac{h}{h+m}$$

V_p —volume proportion of the given parameter

h —number of intersecting points of square grid hitting the selected object

m — number of points falling elsewhere ($h+ m$ was never above 100 as the total number of points in our graticule was 100).

Five fields of ten sections of each placenta were examined (50 fields of each placenta) for determination of volume proportion of a given parameter. For each placenta the average value of the desired parameter was obtained from these 50 fields and recorded in Table No. IV.

Table 1: Figure showing the utilization of square graticule for calculation of volume proportion

Figure 2: Schematic Diagram showing Haugh's graticule used for Histomorphometric study

Figure 3: Low power view of linear graticule

Method of counting of a desired parameter in unit area of placenta: 25 small squares of the square grid were considered as a given fixed area in which a desired parameter (e.g. syncytial knots) was counted under high power objective field. For each placenta the average figure was obtained from 120 such readings. The average figure for each placenta of control and experimental group was duly entered in table IV.

Method for Statistical analysis: The parameter judged for histo-morphometry was subjected to statistical analysis by comparing the data of case (experimental group) versus control and then the difference was assessed for statistical significance using student 't' test. The statistical significance was obtained by 'P' value below 0.05. The data were duly entered in Table for each parameter.

Table 1: Histomorphometry of placenta in both groups

Sample no	Volume proportion of calcification (Ratio)	
	C	E
1	5.50	5.50
2	0	5.45
3	0	4.55
4	0	5.35
5	0	5.25
6	0	5.36
7	0	4.98
8	0	4.65
9	0	5.14
10	0	5.11
11	5.11	5.10
12	5.10	6.01
13	0	5.25
14	0	5.34
15	0	4.28
16	0	4.28
17	0	4.96
18	4.96	5.19
19	0	5.24
20	0	5.36
21	0	5.27
22	0	4.35
23	0	4.95
24	0	5.13
25	5.13	5.20
26	0	5.28
27	0	5.05
28	0	5.26
29	0	4.35
30	0	4.25
31	0	4.19
32	0	4.58
33	0	5.50
34	0	5.32
35	0	4.26
36	0	3.98
37	0	5.21
38	0	4.23
39	0	4.85
40	0	4.61

Table 2: calcification of placenta of both groups

Sample no	Calcification PIH		Sample no	Calcification control	
	Gross	histology		Gross	histology
1	+nt	+nt	1	-nt	+nt
2	-nt	+nt	2	-nt	-nt
3	+nt	+nt	3	-nt	-nt
4	+nt	+nt	4	-nt	-nt
5	-nt	+nt	5	-nt	-nt
6	+nt	+nt	6	-nt	-nt
7	-nt	+nt	7	-nt	-nt
8	-nt	+nt	8	-nt	-nt
9	+nt	+nt	9	-nt	-nt
10	-nt	+nt	10	-nt	-nt
11	-nt	+nt	11	-nt	+nt

12	-nt	+nt	12	-nt	+nt
13	-nt	+nt	13	-nt	-nt
14	-nt	+nt	14	-nt	-nt
15	+nt	+nt	15	-nt	-nt
16	+nt	+nt	16	-nt	-nt
17	-nt	+nt	17	-nt	-nt
18	-nt	+nt	18	-nt	+nt
19	-nt	+nt	19	-nt	-nt
20	-nt	+nt	20	-nt	-nt
21	-nt	+nt	21	-nt	-nt
22	-nt	+nt	22	-nt	-nt
23	-nt	+nt	23	-nt	-nt
24	-nt	+nt	24	-nt	-nt
25	-nt	+nt	25	-nt	+nt
26	-nt	+nt	26	-nt	-nt
27	+nt	+nt	27	-nt	-nt
28	-nt	+nt	28	-nt	-nt
29	-nt	+nt	29	-nt	-nt
30	-nt	+nt	30	-nt	-nt
31	-nt	+nt	31	-nt	-nt
32	-nt	+nt	32	-nt	-nt
33	-nt	+nt	33	-nt	-nt
34	-nt	+nt	34	-nt	-nt
35	-nt	+nt	35	-nt	-nt
36	-nt	+nt	36	-nt	-nt
37	-nt	+nt	37	-nt	-nt
38	+nt	+nt	38	-nt	-nt
39	+nt	+nt	39	-nt	-nt
40	-nt	+nt	40	-nt	-nt

Volume proportion of calcification The control placentae were showing the mean volume proportion of calcification 0.645 and the figure in PIH placenta was 4.954. The increased calcification in PIH cases was statistically significant.

Graph. Mean volume proportion of microscopic calcification of placentae of both groups (control and experiment)

Discussion

Alteration of the progress of pregnancy due to any short or long adverse physiological or pathological condition in mother is reflected not only in foetus but also in other gestational tissues. Pregnancy induced hypertension- 'PIH' is one such altered physiological condition affecting the haemodynamics of pregnancy and placenta is the gestational tissue where the effect of PIH in the form of gross and micro-structural changes as an effect of PIH have been studied in the present case-control study. The subjects in control group had uncomplicated ante and & intranatal period while subjects in experimental group had clinically diagnosed PIH during routine antenatal or intranatal period. [13-16]

The clinical parameter used to diagnose PIH was "Newly diagnosed high blood pressure (140/90 mm Hg or greater) in a previously normotensive pregnant woman, persisting more than two occasions 6 hours apart after 20th week of gestation". The term pregnancy-induced hypertension 'PIH' was popularized by Dr. Jack Pritchard and is used interchangeably with gestational hypertension (Cunningham F G et al 2005). [17,18]

In past, an increase of 30 mm Hg systolic or 15 mm Hg diastolic pressure used to be considered as pregnancy induced hypertension inspite of absolute values being below 140/90 mm Hg. Clinicians deferred this criterion because they did not notice increased risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes (North and colleagues; 1999 Levine and co-workers, 2000) in such cases. We have not included cases of pre-existing hypertension or cases of gestational hypertension before 20th week of gestation in our study as the aetiology and progress of this condition differs from gestational hypertension. [19,20]

We considered age group 20 to 38 years of mothers in our study. This is the most suitable period for reproductive life since all the constituent parts of the reproductive system work to the best of their capacity at this age and there is less interference of other age related compounding factors for assessment of 'Pregnancy induced Hypertension' alone (Majumdar et al 2005 and Cunningham F G et al 2005). [21]

Though it is clinically documented that in elderly Primigravida the incidences of complicated pregnancy such as PIH are more but we have enrolled the subjects irrespective of the parity. [22,23] However we have 80% primiparous subjects enrolled in experimental (PIH) group suggesting higher incidence of PIH in primipara

subjects in our study group It is well documented fact that the incidences of PIH are higher in Primigravida subjects (Cunningham F G et al, 2005).

All enrolled cases have been registered in our institutional hospital and no case has been considered from outside. It is to have uniform criteria for antenatal and intranatal check up and management. [24-26]

Gross calcification on the placental surface (especially on basal plate) was notable in 15% of control and 25% of PIH placenta in the present study. This is similar to the finding of Majumdar S et al (2005) who frequently found grossly calcified foci in the PIH placentae with very few control placentae showing this feature.

Summary and conclusions

The present case control study aimed at identifying microstructural alteration in placenta in condition of Pregnancy induced hypertension 'PIH' has come out with findings in favour of a definite microstructural alterations in placenta.

There was increase in areas of calcification in experimental group of placentae.

Histomorphometrically we have documented that significantly increased volume proportion of calcified areas in experimental group of placentae.

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